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Critical Climate Education is crucial for fast and just transformations

If rapid and just transformations to low-carbon societies are to take place, citizens need to obtain the necessary knowledge and skills to critically examine and choose adequate climate policy options. An emphasis on Critical Climate Education research and implementation is therefore required.

Hanne Svarstad, Alfredo Jornet, Glen P. Peters, Tom G. Griffiths, Tor A. Benjaminsen

Climate mitigation evolves too slowly compared to pledges and ambitions to limit global warming to “well below 2.0 °C”.¹ A range of climate mitigation strategies are implemented or planned, but they vary substantially in terms of their mitigation potential and distribution of burdens.

There is an urgent need for transformation processes to meet targets of climate justice in both time and space. Climate justice in time is between present and future generations, while climate justice in space means justice among the present global population, and with a particular recognition of those who live under conditions of vulnerability and poverty². Policy options in line with aims of strong climate justice are often acknowledged in general terms, but national policy-makers have not prioritised strategies to achieve these aims³.

We argue that a central cause of the unfolding climate crisis is that people do not have access to knowledge and skills to critically examine various national climate options, and thereby be able to demand the necessary climate measures and structural changes for fast and just de-carbonisation.

Critical Climate Education

We suggest the elaboration and implementation of *Critical Climate Education* as a key element in climate strategies. This will require educational research as well as professional development of teachers. Moreover, Critical Climate Education will depend on research and communication of research-based knowledge from a broad spectre of fields and disciplines, including social and natural sciences.⁴

In climate negotiations, public discussions, and in academia, ‘climate justice’ entails a range of equity and fairness concerns related to the distribution of harm caused by climate change as well as the implementation and funding of mitigation and adaptation measures⁵. When strategies and options are chosen, however, justice tends to be neglected.

For several decades the world has instead seen successful efforts from powerful actors such as corporations and governments to divert attention from climate justice, including climate change

49 denialism⁶, delayism⁷, individualisation of responsibility⁸, and various strategies to move the
50 obligations abroad to achieve ‘international cost effectiveness’⁹. In addition, there is the problem of
51 politicians seeking re-election based on ‘here-and-now’ issues¹⁰. A break from this situation will
52 require citizens who are capable of demanding effective and just climate policies.

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55 **Drawing upon critical education scholarship**

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57 In his book *‘Pedagogy of the Oppressed’* (1970), Paulo Freire laid out a foundational approach to
58 critical pedagogy. From growing up in poverty in Brazil, Freire saw the need for urban and rural
59 workers and their children to receive education where they learned to critically reflect on their lived
60 experience, including the nature and reasons for injustices inflicted upon them. Freire’s critical
61 pedagogy was aimed at providing people with tools to understand and develop collective strategies
62 to overcome their oppression.¹¹

63

64 Despite differences with the problems Freire confronted, climate change today constitutes a
65 challenge for which critical pedagogy becomes a necessity. If climate change is to be met with
66 appropriate means, people need to understand and transform the structures, policies, and practices
67 that obstruct sustainable and just alternatives. They need to learn how to find ways that climate
68 change can be met with collective action for effective and just strategies, rather than green washing
69 and neo-colonialism. Without such competence, effective and just climate strategies are not likely to
70 be elaborated, demanded, accepted, or chosen.

71

72 Critical Climate Education is an education approach that needs to draw on critical pedagogy as well
73 as education for democratic citizenship¹², political ecology of education¹³, and relevant contributions
74 to the environmental and climate education scholarship¹⁴.

75

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77 **Critical Climate Education in the Global South and North**

78

79 In Sub-Saharan Africa, children often learn at school that a major cause of climate change is that
80 African villagers cause deforestation, and villagers and pupils are consequently encouraged to plant
81 trees. Such education aligns with other outside pressures against forest use by villagers who are not
82 to blame for the climate crisis. Through interventions often initiated and funded from high emission
83 countries, land is turned into CO₂ sinks through forest conservation and afforestation, while villagers
84 who lose access to land and livelihoods receive limited or no compensation.

85

86 As a contrasting education approach, Critical Climate Education could engage students in examining
87 justice consequences of preservation and tree planting as mitigation. Moreover, the students could
88 discuss the climate justice implications of instead moving the burden of mitigation from African
89 villagers to industries and nation states in the Global North. Critical Climate Education could thereby
90 contribute to decolonise climate education and climate practices.

91

92 In the Global North, Critical Climate Education could involve training in assessing options such as
93 electrification of cars, closing down fossil fuel industries, off-setting national emissions through tree
94 planting schemes in the Global South, and proposals for structural changes towards degrowth
95 economies (Fig. 1).

96

97

98 **Fig. 1** Masters students exploring Critical Climate Education in group work on electrification of cars as
99 climate measure. From left: Vitor Atsushi Nozaki Yano, Vivianne Jour, Innocent Hakizimana Abubakar,
100 Andrea Choroschun. Photo credit: Solfrid Hartberg.

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103 **Linking climate options to contexts and individual choices**

104

105 For climate education to constitute a key climate strategy, there is a need for educational emphasis
106 on options where the main strategies are decided. Critical Climate Education should therefore focus
107 on strengthening citizens' competence in distinguishing between strong and weak climate justice
108 options first of all at the national level, but sometimes also municipal and international levels.

109

110 Critical Climate Education must be elaborated in general as well as in relation to national educational
111 systems and in ways relevant to various levels and populations, while also providing space for
112 teachers and students to shape their own practices. Nevertheless, as the most crucial element across
113 contexts, students should learn how to examine particular climate measures in terms of their
114 consistency or deviation from climate justice in time and space.

115

116 Before learning about how to critically examine specific climate options, students could be
117 introduced to the broad picture of past and current contributions to climate change in their own
118 countries compared to pledges and implementations of emission cuts, as well as factors such as the
119 distribution of historical emissions, and the economic capacity to contribute to global targets.
120 Students could discuss what constitutes a fair share of global needs for climate action in different
121 countries, including their own.

122

123 There are large discrepancies between emissions by rich and poor people¹⁵, and this should provide
124 an important context for discussions of adequate climate measures. Moreover, students need to
125 learn about causes of injustices in climate policy choices, including the role of discursive power.

126

127 Critical Climate Education should also encourage students to extend their learning about climate
128 measures and to investigate the wider context of societal structures that might be necessary to
129 change in order to provide fast and just transformations to low carbon societies. In addition, without
130 individualising climate solutions, students should be invited to reflect on their own role in combating
131 climate change, as citizens engaging in collective action and political decision-making, in work
132 choices, and ways of living.¹⁶

133

134 Fast and just transformations to low-carbon societies are not likely to happen without substantial
135 changes of climate education. Critical Climate Education provides an approach to equip citizens with
136 necessary tools to carry out required transformations.

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